

The nurses' perceptions of caring

behaviors and related factors in cardiac intensive care units in the north of Iran

Las percepciones de las enfermeras sobre los comportamientos de cuidado y los factores relacionados en las unidades de cuidados intensivos cardiacos en el norte de Irán

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Abstract

Introduction and Background: Care is one of the most basic and well-known activities in the nursing system. Nursing focuses on "human health care". Cowin and Warelow believe that a high perception of the concept of care, the way of expressing it, and practising it has a significant impact on the quality of services provided by nurses and, more importantly, on the nursing perception. This study aimed to evaluate nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors and related factors in cardiac intensive care units of educational-medical centres of Gilan University of Medical Sciences. **Methods:** The present study is a cross-sectional and analytical study. The statistical population of the present study included all nurses in cardiac intensive care units of educational-medical centres. Based on the census sampling method, out of the total number of 160 nurses, 152 were included in this study. Data collection tools included 2 sections. 1. Demographic section which included personal, occupational, and social-economic information, 2. The standard Modified CARE-Q. **Results:** The results of the present study showed that nurses' perception score of nursing caring behaviors is about 81.8%, indicating a high perception of the participants. Also, in terms of the relationship between the personal factors and level of perception, gender and organizational status (head nurse compared to nurse $p = 0.24$) showed a significant relationship with the level of perception and regarding the occupational factors; hospital type showed a significant relationship with the level of perception (P

<0.001). Also, the total score of nurses' perception showed a significant relationship with the level of perception, and socio-economic factors showed no significant relationship with the level of perception. Nurses participating in this research pay more attention to the technical aspects of caring than to the emotional and social aspects. The nurses of the intensive care units were more concerned about the physical problems of the hospitalized patients. The availability and timely implementation of treatment instructions was the most important caring behaviour for them and this approach cannot meet all the needs of patients. It is necessary for **Conclusion:** Considering that the nurses participating in this study pay more attention to the technical aspects of caring for the emotional and social aspects, this approach can not meet all the needs of clients and it is necessary for nursing educators and managers in training and planning. Paying special attention to various factors affecting caring behaviours, by emphasizing ethical issues and creating morale, increases the sense of responsibility, strengthens professional ethics and self-efficacy, on the other hand, creating and strengthening counselling services, minimize their problems. So that patients can benefit from better and more appropriate quality services.

Keywords: Perception and nurse, care behaviors, cardiac intensive care units.

Introducción y antecedentes: El cuidado es una de las actividades más básicas y conocidas en el sistema de enfermería. La enfermería se centra en el “cuidado de la salud humana”. Cowin y Warelow creen que una alta percepción del concepto de cuidado, la forma de expresarlo y practicarlo tiene un impacto significativo en la calidad de los servicios prestados por las enfermeras y, lo que es más importante, en la percepción de enfermería. El estudio tuvo por objetivo evaluar las percepciones de las enfermeras sobre los comportamientos de cuidado y los factores relacionados en las unidades de cuidados intensivos cardíacos de los centros médicos educativos de la Universidad de Ciencias Médicas de Gilan. **Métodos:** El presente estudio es un estudio transversal y analítico. La población estadística del presente estudio incluyó a todos los enfermeros de las unidades de cuidados intensivos cardíacos de los centros médico-educativos. Con base en el método de muestreo censal, del total de 160 enfermeros, 152 fueron incluidos en este estudio. Las herramientas de recopilación de datos incluyeron 2 secciones: 1. Apartado demográfico que incluía información personal, ocupacional y socioeconómica, 2. El estándar CARE-Q Modificado. **Resultados:** Los resultados del presente estudio mostraron que el puntaje de percepción de los enfermeros sobre los comportamientos de cuidado de enfermería es de aproximadamente 81,8%, lo que indica una alta percepción de los participantes. Asimismo, en cuanto a la relación entre los factores personales y el nivel de percepción, el género y el estatus organizacional (enfermero jefe frente a enfermero, $p = 0,24$) mostraron una relación significativa con el nivel de percepción, y en cuanto a los factores ocupacionales, el tipo de hospital mostró una relación significativa con el nivel de percepción ($P < 0.001$). Además, la puntuación total de la percepción de las enfermeras mostró una relación significativa con el nivel de percepción, y los factores socioeconómicos no mostraron una relación significativa con el nivel de percepción. Los resultados revelaron que los enfermeros participantes de esta investigación prestan más atención a los aspectos técnicos del cuidado que a los aspectos emocionales y sociales. Las enfermeras de las unidades de cuidados intensivos estaban más preocupadas por los problemas físicos de los pacientes hospitalizados. La disponibilidad y la implementación oportuna de las instrucciones de tratamiento fue el comportamiento de cuidado más importante para ellos y este enfoque no puede satisfacer todas las necesidades de los pacientes. Es necesario que los educadores y gerentes de enfermería presten atención a este tema en la capacitación y la planificación. **Conclusión:** Considerando que los enfermeros que participan en este estudio prestan más atención a los aspectos técnicos del cuidado de los aspectos emocionales y sociales, este enfoque no puede satisfacer todas las necesidades de los clientes y es necesario para los educadores y administradores de enfermería en la formación y planificación. Prestar especial atención a los diversos factores que inciden en las conductas de cuidado, al enfatizar cuestiones éticas y crear moral, aumenta el sentido de responsabilidad, fortalece la ética profesional y la

autoeficacia, por otro lado, al crear y fortalecer los servicios de consejería, se minimizan sus problemas. Para que los pacientes puedan beneficiarse de mejores y más adecuados servicios de calidad.

Palabras clave: Percepción y enfermera, conductas de cuidado, unidades de cuidados intensivos cardíacos.

Introduction

Providing high-quality care and services has been considered a priority in the health care system, especially in the area of nursing services^{1,2}. One of the basic and well-known practices in nursing is “care” and the focus of nursing is on “human health care”^{3,4}. “Care” is a complex and multidimensional concept that stimulates personal growth and helps people to survive in the face of various stressful events⁵. In other words, care means nursing and nursing means care and it is an underlying part of the nursing profession⁶⁻⁷. Caring behaviours are technical, physical, psychological, social, and emotional actions that include a variety of characteristics and actions (words, thoughts, feelings, insights, actions, body language, touch, actions, and methods). Thus, care requires the personal, spiritual, moral, and to some extent social activities of the nurses⁸. One of these significant competencies is the nurse’s perception of care. Cowin and Warelow believe that a high perception of the concept of care, the way of expressing and practising it has a significant impact on the quality of services provided by nurses and, more importantly, on the nursing perception and understanding⁹⁻¹⁰. Perceptual inputs are automatically translated into the output of corresponding behaviours. According to the Skinner study in 1938, perception directly induces behavior¹¹. Identifying the type of nurses and patients’ perceptions of the importance of caring behaviors enables nurses to provide better care for patients by recognizing behaviors that lead to better nurse-client interaction and increase patient satisfaction with nursing services¹². Perception has a direct and effective relationship with an individual’s behaviour. In clinical settings, emotional communication and patients’ perception and awareness of patients’ cultural and social differences lead to better performance of nurses¹³. In this regard, Cowin and Warelow believe that a high perception of the concept of care, the way of expressing and practising it has a significant impact on the quality of services provided by nurses and more importantly on the perception and understanding of nursing^{14,15}. Bassett also argues that nurses’ perception of their role as caregivers is essential to discussing the concept of care¹⁶.

The intensive care unit is one of the units in which nurses play a major role. This unit is one of the most critical professional units of the hospital, and due to the complex and critical conditions of patients, caring behaviours have a special importance¹⁷. Thus, it is the safest place for critically ill patients. Preserving the patient’s life and providing the highest quality care activities along with maintaining patient convenience is one of the most important goals of intensive care units. Patients admitted to these units need advanced

and high-quality care due to the wide range of acute and critical illnesses. Only in such conditions, patients in the intensive care unit will benefit more compared to patients in general units¹⁸. Hence, nurses' perception is important and necessary to address this issue¹⁹. In this regard, the need for intensive care is increasing in many countries around the world. Based on the statistics, the number of Intensive Care Unit (ICU) beds is estimated at 15% in the United States and 30% in the United Kingdom in the last 10 years, and 57% for the next few years in Canada²⁰.

Thus, support and paying attention to patients is an important aspect of nursing care that has a fundamental value for the nursing profession. Differences in nurses' caring behaviors in different institutions and different countries have led nursing researchers to study caring behaviors to identify nurses' perceptions of this key role to enhance the patient support behaviors^{21, 22, 23} (Comment: This sentence is created above. Change or delete). Intensive care units are one of the most stressful places in the hospital²⁴ and are one of the professional units in which nurses play a major role in providing critical care²⁵. In other words, the intensive care unit is a place, where patients with the word conditions are treated because of its special facilities. These units face daily challenges in achieving stability, work pressure, safety, and quality of care⁷⁵. Also, nurses experience more ethical decisions in the care and treatment of patients in critical situations than physicians due to the physical work stress and severe psychological stress in the intensive care unit⁸³.

Hence, they require knowledge and scientific support, a strong attitude and skills for clinical decisions, and the use of advanced equipment and facilities²⁶. Having a clear perception of the concept of "care" is essential for the scientific development of nursing²⁷. In general, it should be noted that professional nursing care is an important factor in providing high-quality care and can guarantee the quality of care²⁸. Since nurses' perception of caring behaviors and related factors is the first step to correcting inappropriate behaviors and providing better nursing care and improving the quality of nursing care²⁹, the present study was conducted to evaluate nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors and related factors in cardiac intensive care units of educational-medical centres in Gilan University of Medical Sciences. In this regard, the main question of this research was what is the score of nurses' perception of caring behaviors in the areas of availability, explaining and facilitating, convenience, prediction, reliable communication, supervising, and follow-up in cardiac intensive care units in the educational-medical centres of Gilan University of Medical Sciences and what are the socio-economic, personal, and occupational factors associated with nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors.

Materials and methods

The present study is cross-sectional analytical research conducted on nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors and related factors in cardiac intensive care units of educational-medical centres of Gilan University of Medical Sciences in 2020. The statistical population in this study included all 160 nurses in cardiac intensive care units of educational-medical centres of Gilan University of Medical Sciences, selected using a census sampling method.

Data collection tools

Data collection tools in the present study included 2 sections. 1. Demographic section which included personal, occupational, and social-economic information, 2. The standard Modified CARE-Q. In the section on personal-occupational and social-economic information, variables such as age, gender, marital status, number of children, economic status, amount of monthly overtime, education level, university type, place of residence, employment history, history of working in the intensive care unit, hospital type, organizational post, employment status, shift work, interest in the nursing profession, interest in working in the cardiac intensive care unit, attending retraining courses, the possibility of career advancement, simultaneous employment, and number of beds in the evaluated unit. The Modified CARE-Q 50-item questionnaire was also used to assess nurses' perceptions. This questionnaire was designed based on a seven-point Likert scale ranging from "least important" to "most important". This questionnaire has 6 areas of availability (6 questions), explaining and facilitating (6 questions), convenience (9 questions), prediction (5 questions), reliable communication (16 questions), and supervising and follow-up (8 questions). To determine the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the opinions of 15 professors and faculty members of the School of Nursing and Midwifery in the Shahid Beheshti University of Rasht were used, and after receiving their comments and opinions, the necessary corrections were applied. After calculating the coefficient of variation ratio (CVR) index for each of the questions, according to the Lawshe table, it was found that the questions had the necessary validity (CVR > 62%). Also, by calculating the CVR index for each question, the range of changes was obtained between 0.7 and 1.

Thus, questions with CVI between 0.7 and 0.8 were seriously reviewed, questions with CVI between 0.8 and 0.9 were partially reviewed, and questions above 0.9 were used directly without any review. Also, regarding the reliability of the questionnaire, the test-retest method was used. In this regard, a questionnaire was distributed among 20 nurses and collected after answering, and after two weeks, it was distributed again among the same 15 people and collected. The reliability coefficient of the questionnaire was obtained at 99% and the Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) agreement coefficient was obtained at 0.72 and was statistically significant ($P = 0.019$). Cronbach's alpha

coefficient was also used to evaluate the internal consistency of the questions. The questionnaires were distributed among 20 people and their total value was obtained at 0.95 and in the range between 0.30 and 0.90, indicating the high internal consistency of the questionnaire questions to determine the care evaluation score.

Also, to collect data in field studies, after explaining the aim of the study to the research samples and obtaining their consent, and explaining the way of filling up the questionnaire, the researcher submitted the questionnaires to the participants asked them to answer the questions accurately. The questionnaires were completed in the presence of the researcher and concerning the letter dated 2020/9/25 and the code of ethics of IR.GUMS.REC.295 / 1399. Also, due to the prevalence of the COVID-19 virus and the restrictions on traffic, sampling was done over three months and 152 nurses from cardiac intensive care units of Gilan University of Medical Sciences participated in the study, but 8 nurses did not complete the questionnaire.

Data analysis method

The values of quantitative variables (age, number of children, employment history, history of working in intensive care unit, amount of monthly overtime) were shown as mean \pm standard deviation, and values of qualitative variables were shown as frequency (percentage). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was also used to evaluate the normality and equality of variances for use in the independent t-test. To determine the score of nurses' perception of care, mean and standard deviation indices were used with the lowest and highest scores and a 95% mean confidence interval. Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to compare the perception scores due to abnormality. Also, to determine the factors related to nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors, a multiple linear regression model was used and the data were analyzed using SPSS-21 software and the significance level was considered at 0.05.

Results

Our results indicate that the age of the samples was 35.1 ± 8.8 and the minimum age was 22 years old and the maximum age was 60 years old. The majority were female in terms of gender (95.4%) and married (70.4%) in terms of marriage. In investigating the number of children in non-single people, 24.6% had no child and the majority (44.6%) had one child. Also, according to the employment history of nurses, they had 10.1 ± 7.6 years. The minimum employment history was half a year and the maximum was 30 years. The majority had 5 years or less of employment history (33.6%). The history of working in the intensive care unit were 6.9 ± 6 years.

In terms of hospital type, the majority were from Heshmat Hospital with 18.4%, Pirooz Lahijan Hospital with 13.2%, and Ansari Rudsar Hospital with 9.2%. In terms of organizational

costs, the majority of them were clinical nurses (90.1%). In terms of employment status, the majority of them had official employment status (48%), followed by project-based (27%) and contractual (11.2%), respectively. In terms of work shifts, the majority of nurses had rotating shifts (84.2%). Also, 91.5% of them were interested in working in the cardiac intensive care unit. In terms of the history of participation in intensive care unit retraining courses, 69.7% have participated in retraining courses. Also, in terms of career advancement, only 10.5% of nurses stated that they can never have career advancement and 89.5% stated that there is career advancement in the workplace. In terms of the number of beds, the majority (34.2%) of them covered eight beds. In terms of interaction with the physician, the majority (63.2%) of them stated that they always establish this interaction, and in terms of interaction with the person in charge, the majority of them (67.8%) stated that they have always had this interaction. Also, based on the nurses' economic status, the majority of them had moderate (56.6%) economic status. In terms of overtime, the majority of them had less than 50 hours of overtime (50.4%). At the education level, the majority of them (92.8%) had bachelor's degrees and the majority of them (59.2%) were graduated from Azad University. In investigating the situation of compliance with different conditions, the majority of them (59.9%) have always had this compliance, and in examining the indigenesness status of the working place, the majority of them (78.3%) were indigenous.

Table 1. Assessing the normality of nurses' perception scores of caring behaviors in each area and in total

Row	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	statistic	df	P-Value	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Availability	0.111	152	0.0001	0.942	152	0.0001
Explaining and facilitation	0.160	152	0.0001	0.932	152	0.0001
Convenience	0.091	152	0.003	0.955	152	0.0001
Prediction	0.175	152	0.0001	0.905	152	0.0001
Reliable communication	0.113	152	0.0001	0.950	152	0.0001
Supervising and follow-up	0.177	152	0.0001	0.887	152	0.0001
Nurses' perception of caring behaviors	0.1090	152	0.0001	0.940	152	0.0001

Based on the information in Table 1, according to Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests, the distribution of scores did not follow the normal distribution. Therefore, non-parametric tests were used to analyze the data.

Table 2. Statistical indices of nurses' scores of perception of caring behaviors in each area and in total

Row	Nurses' perception of caring behaviors	Mean	SD	median	Min	Max	95% confidence interval	
							Lower bound	Upper bound
Score of nurses' perception areas	Availability (6-42)	37.04	3.44	37.00	28.00	42.00	36.49	37.59
	Explaining and facilitating (6-42)	35.98	4.24	36.00	19.00	42.00	35.30	36.66
	Convenience (9-63)	52.49	6.43	53.00	33.00	63.00	51.46	53.52
	Predictions (5-35)	29.40	3.78	30.00	16.00	35.00	28.80	30.01
	Reliable communication (16-112)	90.74	12.30	93.00	53.00	112.00	88.77	92.71
	Supervising and follow-up (8-56)	49.86	5.26	51.00	31.00	56.00	49.02	50.70
	Total (50-350)	295.51	31.94	299.00	198.00	350.00	290.39	300.63
Balanced score of areas of nurses' perception	Availability (1-7)	6.17	0.57	6.17	4.67	7.00	6.08	6.27
	Explaining and facilitating (1-7)	6.00	0.71	6.00	3.17	7.00	5.88	6.11
	Convenience (1-7)	5.83	0.71	5.89	3.67	7.00	5.72	5.95
	Predictions (1-7)	5.88	0.76	6.00	3.20	7.00	5.76	6.00
	Reliable communication (1-7)	5.67	0.77	5.81	3.31	7.00	5.55	5.79
	Supervising and follow-up (8-51-76)	6.23	0.66	6.38	3.88	7.00	6.13	6.34
	Total (1-7)	5.91	0.64	5.98	3.96	7.00	5.81	6.01

As shown in Table 2, the mean total score of nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors is in the range of 50 to 350. The score that can be obtained from the questionnaire is 295.5 ± 31.9 the lowest score was 198 and the highest score was 350. The mean percentage of the total obtainable score of perception was about 81.8% (the perception score is above the 75th percentile). In examining the balanced score of the area, the highest perception of nurses in the area of supervising and follow-up had a mean of 66 ± 6.23 with a median of 6.38 and the lowest perception score in the area of reliable communication from the obtainable range of 1 to 7 was 77 ± 5.67 with a median of 5.81.

Chart 1. Nurses' perception scores in different areas

According to bar Chart 1, nurses' perception score was in the highest value in the three areas of supervising and follow-up, availability and facilitation and in the lowest in the areas of reliable communication, convenience and prediction. According to the Friedman test, there was a statistically significant difference between nurses' perceptions in the studied areas ($P < 0.001$).

Table 3. Correlation between nurses' perception score of caring behaviors in each area and total with some personal, occupational and socioeconomic variables

Row		Availability	Explaining and facilitating	Convenience	Prediction	Reliable communication	Supervising and follow-up	Nurses' perception of caring behaviors
Age	correlation coefficient	0.038	0.111	0.202	0.113	0.104	0.076	0.132
	P-Value	0.641	0.174	0.013	0.166	0.202	0.355	0.105
	N	152	152	152	152	152	152	152
Number of children	correlation coefficient	0.074	0.212	0.216	0.186	0.154	0.186	0.186
	P-Value	0.439	0.026	0.023	0.052	0.108	0.052	0.052
	N	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
Employment history	correlation coefficient	0.037	0.091	0.181	0.120	0.109	0.068	0.120
	P-Value	0.655	0.266	0.026	0.141	0.180	0.409	0.139
	N	152	152	152	152	152	152	152
History of working in ICU	correlation coefficient	0.094	0.219	0.279	0.181	0.117	0.091	0.178
	P-Value	0.249	0.007	0.0001	0.026	0.152	0.266	0.029
	N	152	152	152	152	152	152	152
Number of unit beds	correlation coefficient	0.018	-0.049	-0.008	-0.106	-0.052	0.020	-0.032
	P-Value	0.828	0.549	0.919	0.194	0.0528	0.808	0.696
	N	152	152	152	152	152	152	152
Monthly over time	correlation coefficient	-0.053	-0.085	-0.162	-0.126	-0.112	-0.184	-0.135
	P-Value	0.565	0.357	0.078	0.173	0.224	0.045	0.144
	N	119	119	119	119	119	119	119

* Spearman's correlation coefficient

Based on the information in Table 3, the nurses' perception score of caring behaviors was significantly and positively correlated with the number of children ($P = 5.5$, $r = 186\%$), and the history of working in the intensive care unit ($r = 178$, $P = 29$). The correlation between nurses' perception areas scores and quantitative variables shows that all areas except for the areas of reliable communication and availability had a significant positive correlation with the number of children. Also, the history of working in the ICU has a significant positive correlation with the areas of explaining and facilitating, convenience, and prediction. The age of nurses had a significant positive correlation with convenience score ($r = 222$, $P = 13$). However, the amount of monthly overtime had a significant and inverse correlation with the supervising and follow-up score ($r=184\%$, $P=45\%$).

Table 4. Comparison of nurses' perception scores of caring behaviors in terms of personal factors

Row		nurses' perception scores of caring behaviors			P-Value
		Mean	SD	median	
Age	Less than 30 years	290.94	32.96	294.00	0.423**
	30-35	292.97	31.22	298.00	
	35-40	299.74	31.49	305.00	
	40-45	298.95	26.66	300.00	
	45 years and older	301.14	36.47	302.00	
Gender	male	322.57	31.76	323.00	0.023*
	female	294.21	31.47	299.00	
Marital status	single	291.26	31.08	297.00	0.487**
	Married	297.49	31.80	300.00	
	Divorced	284.67	53.69	310.00	
Number of children	0.00	291.04	35.90	296.00	0.158**
	1.00	291.82	32.99	299.00	
	2.00	311.74	26.36	313.00	
	3.00	304.00	16.40	300.00	
	4.00	295.50	12.02	295.50	

* Mann-Whitney U test ** Kruskal-Wallis test

As shown in Table 4, the total score of nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors based on gender was significant $P = 23\%$, so male nurses had higher mean scores than female nurses.

Table 5. Comparison of nurses' perception of caring behaviors scores in terms of occupational factors

Row	nurses' perception of caring behaviors				P-Value		
	Mean	SD	median				
Employment history	5 years and less	290.12	33.96	294.00	0.229**		
	6-11	300.00	29.47	303.00			
	11-16	292.98	32.18	299.50			
	16 years and more	305.24	28.99	304.00			
History of working in ICU	2 years and less	287.45	34.52	295.00	0.196**		
	More than 2-5 years	296.19	32.87	297.00			
	5-10	299.36	31.26	303.00			
	More than 10 years	301.66	26.55	300/00			
Hospital type	Dr. Pirooz Hospital of Lahijan	290.70	30.36	298.50	<0.001**		
	Shahid Beheshti Hospital of Astara	312.64	25.98	305.50			
	Ghadir Hospital of Siahkal	301.57	10.37	297.00			
	Ansari Hospital of Rudsar	299.50	12.09	301.50			
	Shahid Hosseinpoor Hospital of Langarud	295.73	13.62	297.00			
	Shahid Nourani Hospital of Talesh	322.40	19.68	322.00			
	Dr. Heshmat Hospital of Rasht	267.68	44.03	270.00			
	Shahid Dr. Beheshti Hospital of Anzali	280.60	35.10	277.50			
	Kowsar Hospital of Astaneh	310.00	20.94	316.50			
	Valiasr Hospital of Rudsar	293.70	19.78	291.00			
	Imam Khomeini Hospital of Soomesara	309.33	17.28	312.00			
	Imam Hassan Mojtaba Hospital of Fooman	305.71	16.97	307.00			
	Organizational post	Head nurse	311.55	23.41		310.00	0.148**
		staff nurse	280.50	35.69		270.00	
nurse		294.66	32.19	299.00			
Employment history	Official	299.64	29.11	300.00	0.146**		
	In treaty	289.53	27.38	296.00			
	Contractual	301.82	44.15	314.00			
	Corporate	304.30	17.50	305.50			
Work shift	Project-based	286/80	36.27	291/00	0.732**		
	Moring shift	295/48	34.14	294/00			
	Night shift	311/33	25.79	304.00			
Interested in nursing	Rotating	295/15	31.83	299.00	0.099*		
	Yes	296/50	32.40	300.00			
History of participating in retaining courses related to cardiac intensive care	No	285/00	25.20	290.00	0.178*		
	Yes	296/55	34.43	302.00			
Possibility of career advancement	Never	293/13	25.47	296.00	0.496**		
	often	296.00	24.99	299.50			
	Always	296.74	35.09	302.50			
Simultaneously working in other places	Yes	293.38	28.74	295.50	0.254*		
	No	307.35	28.14	302.00			
Number of unit beds	Yes	294.02	32.17	299.00	0.962**		
	4.00	300.84	17.18	299.00			
	6.00	299.27	14.38	300.00			
	8.00	294.23	31.71	296.50			
	12.00	288.18	52.86	303.00			
Interaction with physician	16.00	296.13	27.34	300.00	0.063**		
	Never	296.50	7.78	296.50			
	often	286.81	33.06	294.50			
Interaction with the person in charge	Always	300.39	30.73	300.00	0/087**		
	Never	295.00	24.25	291.00			
	often	286.39	34.11	293.00			
	Always	299.60	30.52	300.00			

* Mann-Whitney U test ** Kruskal-Wallis test

According to Table 5, there was a significant difference in nurses' total perception scores based on the hospital type ($P < 0.001$). Perception scores in Talesh, Beheshti Astara and Kowsar Astaneh hospitals had the highest mean, and Heshmat, Shahid Beheshti Hospital of Anzali and Pirooz Lahijan hospitals had the lowest mean.

Table 6. Comparison of nurses' perception scores of caring behaviors in terms of socio-economic factors

Row		nurses' perception scores of caring behaviors			
		Mean	SD	Median	P-Value
Economic status	Completely inappropriate	265.50	13.44	265.50	0.116**
	Inappropriate	279.00	37.01	276.00	
	Moderate	298.90	29.39	300.50	
	appropriate	294.58	34.23	297.00	
Monthly overtime	50 hours and less	296.93	32.08	299.00	0.741**
	50.1-100	292.84	34.76	297.00	
	100 hours and more	287.36	38.79	297.50	
Education level	Bachelor	294.77	32.44	297.00	0.306*
	Master	305.09	23.81	304.00	
University type	Public University	294.15	30.50	299.50	0.781*
	Azad University	296.46	33.03	297.00	
A person able to adapt to different situations	Sometimes	298.25	29.00	300.00	0.444*
	Always	293.68	33.80	297.00	
Indigenoussness	yes	295.57	33.25	299.00	0.681*
	no	295.30	27.14	297.00	

* Mann-Whitney U test ** Kruskal-Wallis test

According to Table 6, scores of nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors in any of these variables are not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$).

Table 7. The most important predictors of nurses' perception scores of caring behaviors are based on a multiple linear generalized regression model

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval		Hypothesis Test
			Lower	Upper	Sig.
Constant	315.015	7.0390	301.219	328.811	0.0001
Male	30.732	10.5880	9.980	51.484	0.004
Female	0
Dr. Pirooz Hospital of Lahijan	-24.315	9.1108	-42.172	-6.458	0.008
Shahid Beheshti Hospital of Astara	-5.894	9.7087	-24.923	13.134	0.544
Ghadir Hospital of Siahkal	-16.098	12.0381	-39.692	7.497	0.181
Ansari Hospital of Rudsar	-16.842	9.8431	-36.134	2.450	0.087
Shahid Hosseinpour Hospital of Langarud	-20.977	10.4841	-41.525	-0.428	0.045
Dr. Heshmat Hospital of Rasht	-52.112	8.3869	-68.550	-35.674	0.0001
Shahid Dr. Beheshti Hospital of Anzali	-36.490	10.8461	-57.748	-15.232	0.001
Kowsar Hospital of Astane	-6.873	10.7711	-27.984	14.238	0.523
Valiasr Hospital of Rudsar	-23.173	10.7711	-44.284	-2.062	0.031
Imam Khomeini Hospital of Soomesara	-6.044	12.8723	-31.273	19.185	0.639
Imam Hassan Mojtaba Hospital of Fooman	-11.955	12.0381	-35.549	11.639	0.321
Shahid Nourani Hospital of Talesh
Organizational post (nurse)	18.578	8.2163	2.474	34.682	0.024
Organizational post staff)	2.174	13.6796	-24.637	28.986	0.874
Nurses	30.732	10.5880	9.980	51.484	0.004

According to Table 7, among the personal-occupational-social-economic variables, only the variables of gender (male nurse compared to female nurse) ($P = 0.004$), organizational status (head nurse compared to nurse) ($P = 0.024$) were statistically significant. Male nurses had higher perception scores than female nurses ($P = 0.004$, $B = 30.73$) and also

head nurses had higher perception scores than clinical nurses ($\beta=18.57$ and $P = 0.024$). Hospital type in the analysis showed a significant relationship with the nurses' perception.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate a high perception of nurses participating in the study about caring behaviors. Also, investigating personal, occupational and socio-economic variables in nurses showed that in the personal variables, only the gender of nurses was significant so male nurses had a higher mean score than female nurses. Also, in occupational variables, organizational posts (head nurses compared to nurses) had a greater perception of care. However, no significant relationship was found between the socio-economic variables and nurses' perceptions of patient care. Also, investigating the statistical indices of nurses' perception score of caring behaviours in each of the areas showed that the mean total score of nurses' perception of caring behaviours from an obtainable score of 50 to 350 was 295 ± 31.9 , and based on the percentage, the mean of the total score was about 81.8% (the perception score is above 75th percentile), which means high perception in the participants. The highest perception of nurses was in the area of "supervising and follow-up" and the lowest score was in the area of "reliable communication". Also, the results of nurses' perception scores were at the highest level in three areas of "supervising and follow-up", "availability" and "facilitating" and at the lowest level in the areas of "reliable communication", "convenience" and "prediction". There was a statistically significant difference among nurses' perceptions in the studied areas ($p < 0.001$). Accordingly, the results suggest that nurses' perception of caring behaviors has been at a high level. These results were supported by the studies conducted in Ireland⁸⁶ and Ethiopia³⁰. It suggests that nurses perceive observable aspects of caring behaviour more than caring behaviour. This result is similar to a study conducted in Gondor and Sweden³¹. However, this result is in contrast with the result of a study conducted in Japan³² and Jordan³³, in which nurses reported low levels of perception of caring behaviors. This inconsistency might be attributed to differences in organizations and the attitude of nurses in different countries³⁴.

Also, the results of the present study compared to similar studies conducted in Western countries indicate differences between perceiving nursing caring behaviours in this study and similar studies conducted by von Essen et al. (1991) and Smith and Sullivan (1997), which stated that nurses consider emotional caring behaviours more important than physical behaviors^{35,36}. The results of studies conducted by Forouzi³⁷ and Bajelani³⁸ (comment: the references are missing and do not correspond to the number) and Khademian and Wieshsfar³⁹ and Mack Oven⁴⁰ showed that the physical-technical dimension of care is more important and Viklin⁴¹ and O'Connell⁴² concluded that nurses pay more attention to the psycho-emotional dimension of care⁴³. These results are in contrast to the studies conducted by Salimi⁴⁴, Essen

and Sewden⁴⁵ and Farmer⁴⁶, in which the importance of both aspects of care was the same. This study also found that nurses' demographic factors were not significantly related to the distribution of their responses to the technical or psychosocial dimensions of caring behaviors.

Moreover, Khademian et al.⁴⁷ attributed to these differences to cultural differences in the societies. In our culture, more attention is paid to the physical dimension of patients and their mental and psychological dimensions are not considered by the medical staff. Also, another feature of the care system is that the nurses are not familiar with all the needs of the patient, and communication between the patient and the nurse is not effective. Therefore, providing training in this area and conducting future research to examine this issue more closely seems to be necessary. Also, to answer the second question on identifying personal factors related to nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors in cardiac intensive care units of Gilan University of Medical Sciences", the results of investigating the correlation between nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors in each area as well as the total score and personal, occupational and social variables showed that nurses' score of perception of caring behaviors had a significant positive correlation with the number of children and history of working in the intensive care unit. Also, all areas positively and significantly correlated with the number of children except for the score of the area of reliable communication and availability, which were not significantly correlated with the number of children.

The age of nurses had a significant positive correlation with the area of "convenience", but the amount of monthly overtime had a significant inverse correlation with the area of "supervising and follow-up". Also, comparing the score of nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors in terms of personal variables showed that the total score of nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors in terms of gender was significant, so male nurses had higher mean scores than female nurses ($P < 0.05$). Also, the results of field data showed a significant relationship between the number of children and history of working in the intensive care unit and nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors. There was a significant relationship between the number of children and history of working in the intensive care unit and nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors. However, Asadi et al. (2014) did not find a relationship between nurses' demographic characteristics and their perception⁴⁸, which is also confirmed in the research conducted by Kotronoulas et al. (2009)⁴⁹. Also, in the research conducted by Khademian on a group of nurses, demographic factors (age, gender, employment history, and position) were not significantly associated with the perception of the importance of caring behaviors⁵⁰. However, consistent with the results of the present study, Tarbiat Nazloo et al. (2019) observed a relationship between demographic variables and perception of caring behaviors, gender, age (more perception of caring behaviors in males), employment history in intensive care units, employment status and employment history and nurses' perception of caring behaviors⁷⁸.

Regarding gender, since males experience less stress, this difference can affect patients' way of management and their perception of caring behaviours. Also, the results of studies have shown that more employment history in nurses causes them to have a better perception of the care provided to patients⁸⁶. However, studies in this area are limited and to consolidate the results of the present study, future studies must be conducted to examine the level of perception of nurses due to demographic differences so that based on the relationship between different demographic variables in nurses, the next effective steps to be taken to improve their perception level of caring. Also, regarding the issue of identifying occupational factors related to nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors in cardiac intensive care units of Gilan University of Medical Sciences", the nurses' perception of caring behaviors in terms of occupational factors was examined and the results showed that the perception score of all nurses had a significant difference in terms of hospital type ($P < 0.001$). Accordingly, the perception score in Talesh Hospital, Shahid Beheshti Hospital of Astara, and Kowsar Hospital of Astaneh had the highest mean and Dr Heshmat Hospital of Rasht, Dr Shahid Beheshti Hospital of Anzali and Dr Pirooz Hospital of Lahijan had the lowest mean perception. Also, the score of nurses' perception did not show a significant relationship with employment history, history of working in ICU, organizational post, employment status, work shift, having an interest in nursing, history of participation in retraining courses, possibility of career advancement, simultaneously working in other places, several units, interaction with physician and interaction with the manager ($P > 0.05$). In the present study, there was no significant difference between job-related characteristics and nurses' perceptions. However, in the study conducted by Dizachi et al. (2014), officially employed nurses compared to nurses with a contractual employment status considered establishing trustful communication with the patient and giving an explanation to the patient important and the researchers believed that as we get closer to official employment status to contractual employment status, due to increased work experience, especially in ICU, the ability to communicate well with patients increases³⁷. Also, based on the Ethiopian study, it was found that job satisfaction is directly associated with the level of nurses' perception of caring behaviors³⁶. Thus, it is essential to investigate the occupational factors related to the perception of nursing behaviors in nurses. Also, regarding the issue of determining socio-economic factors related to nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors in cardiac intensive care units of Gilan University of Medical Sciences, comparing nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors was not correlated with any of these variables (Economic status, monthly overtime, education level, university type, and ability to adapt to different conditions, ingeniousness of workplace) ($P > 0.05$). Also, among the personal, occupational, social, and economic variables, only the variable of gender (male nurses compared to female nurses) and organizational post (head nurse compared to nurse) were statistically significant. However, further studies are needed to confirm the results of the present study.

In terms of the nurses' hospital type, perceptions of nurses working in Shahid Hosseinpour Hospital of Langarud, Dr Heshmat Hospital, Dr Beheshti Hospital of Anzali and Dr Pirooz Hospital of Lahijan had a lower perception score than the reference hospital (Shahid Nourani Hospital of Talesh). The results of the present study revealed that the nurses participating in this study pay more attention to the routine technical aspects of caring for the emotional and social aspects. It seems that nurses of the intensive care units were more concerned about the physical problems of the hospitalized patients. Availability and timely implementation of treatment instructions was the most important caring behaviour for them and this approach cannot meet all the needs of clients it is necessary for nursing educators and managers to pay attention to this issue in training and planning. Thus, it should be noted that many factors are influential in caring behaviours and nursing managers can increase the sense of responsibility, strengthen professional ethics and self-efficacy by emphasizing ethical issues and by creating and strengthening counselling services, and minimizing their problems.

Conclusion

In the present study conducted to investigate nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors and related factors in cardiac intensive care units of Gilan University of Medical Sciences, it was found that nurses' mean perceptions of caring behaviors in the areas of availability, explaining and facilitating, convenience, prediction, reliable communication and supervising and follow-up in the cardiac intensive care units of Gilan University of Medical Sciences was about 81.8% (perception score is higher than 75th percentile). It means a high perception of the nurses studied. The highest perception of nurses was in the area of supervising and follow-up and the lowest score of perception was in the area of reliable communication. Considering the personal factors related to nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors, it was found that the total score of nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors was significant in terms of gender, so those male nurses had a higher mean score than female nurses ($P < 0.05$). Considering the occupational factors related to nurses' perceptions of caring behaviours, the results showed that the total perception score of nurses was significantly different in terms of the type of hospital ($P < 0.001$) and the perception score in nurses working in Nourani Hospital of Talesh, Beheshti Hospital of Astara and Kowsar Hospital of Astaneh had the highest mean and the perception score in nurses working in Heshmat Hospital, Shahid Beheshti Hospital of Anzali and Pirooz Hospital of Lahijan had the lowest mean.

Also, the total score of nurses' perception showed no significant relationship with employment history, history of working in ICU, organizational post, employment status, work shift, having an interest in nursing, history of participating in cardiac intensive related retraining, the possibility of

career advancement, simultaneously working at another place, number of beds in unit, interaction with physician and interaction with the person in charge. In addition, considering the socio-economic factors related to nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors, the results showed that nurses' perceptions of caring behaviors were not significantly associated with any of the variables of economic status, monthly overtime, level of education, university type, having the ability to adapt to different conditions, and indigenouness of working place. In general, according to the results of this study, it is recommended for future studies examine the impact of this issue on other working conditions of nurses. Also, since this study was performed on nurses, it is recommended for future studies to examine other groups of medical staff. Also, since no significant relationship was observed between demographic and occupational factors and nurses' perceptions, it is recommended for future studies to conduct this study with a larger sample size and analyze training methods to improve perceptions in nurses.

Compliance with ethical guidelines:

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery (Ethics Code: IRGUMS.REC.295/1399 All ethical principles are considered in this article. The participants were informed about the purpose of the research and its implementation stages. They were also assured about the confidentiality of their information and were free to leave the study whenever they wished, and if desired, the research results would be available to them.

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Author contribution:

Conceptualization and methodology: Lida Sadeghi Lotfabad; Writing – original draft: Ehsan kazemnezhad leyli; Data collection: Kobra Salami Kohan; Data analysis: Asieh Sedighi chafjiri Ramin soulati masouleh Supervision: All authors.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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